

Appendix C

Appendix C shows the text alignments for all alignments performed using CLUSTAL. Results are shown for each of the three positive GSL samples compared to the expected amplicon sequences and control sample amplicon sequences for each filarial species.

CLUSTAL 0(1.2.4) multiple sequence alignment

```
A.odend_synthetic      CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGGAAAGTTACGATAGATTGTACTCT      60
A.odendhali_28S        CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGGAAAGTTACGATAGATTGTACTCT      60
A.viteae_28S           CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGAAGAGTTACGATAGATTGTACTTT      60
A.vit_synthetic        -----CATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGAAGAGTTACGATAGATTGTACTTT      54
D.rep_synthetic        -----TCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTATGGTAGATTATACTTT      56
D.repens_28S           -CAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTATGGTAGATTATACTTT      59
D.imm_synthetic        -----GGTGAAAAAAGTTACGATATGTTATACTTT      30
D.immitis_28S         -CAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTACGATATGTTATACTTT      59
G9_amplicon            CTAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTACGATATGTTATACTTT      60
                        ***** * ***** * ** ** **** *

A.odend_synthetic      GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      120
A.odendhali_28S        GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      120
A.viteae_28S           GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      120
A.vit_synthetic        GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      114
D.rep_synthetic        GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      116
D.repens_28S           GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      119
D.imm_synthetic        GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      90
D.immitis_28S         GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      119
G9_amplicon            GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      120
                        *****

A.odend_synthetic      TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 157
A.odendhali_28S        TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 157
A.viteae_28S           TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 157
A.vit_synthetic        TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 151
D.rep_synthetic        TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 153
D.repens_28S           TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 156
D.imm_synthetic        TATGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAGAAT 130
D.immitis_28S         TATGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 156
G9_amplicon            TATGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAGA-- 158
                        ** *****
```

CLUSTAL O(1.2.4) multiple sequence alignment

```
Aodend      CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGGAAAAGTTACGATAGATTGTACTCT 60
A.odendhali CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGGAAAAGTTACGATAGATTGTACTCT 60
A.vit       -----CATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGAAGAGTTACGATAGATTGTACTTT 54
A.viteae    CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGAAGAGTTACGATAGATTGTACTTT 60
D.rep       ----TCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTATGGTAGATTATACTTT 56
D.repens    -CAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTATGGTAGATTATACTTT 59
D.imm       -----GGTGAAAAAAGTTACGATATGTTATACTTT 30
G16         CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTACGATATGTTATACTTT 60
D.immitis   -CAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTACGATATGTTATACTTT 59
                                     ***** * ***** * ** ** ***** *
```

```
Aodend      GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA 120
A.odendhali GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA 120
A.vit       GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA 114
A.viteae    GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA 120
D.rep       GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA 116
D.repens    GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA 119
D.imm       GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA 90
G16         GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA 120
D.immitis   GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA 119
*****
```

```
Aodend      TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 157
A.odendhali TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 157
A.vit       TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 151
A.viteae    TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 157
D.rep       TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 153
D.repens    TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 156
D.imm       TATGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAGAAT 130
G16         TATGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAGA-- 158
D.immitis   TATGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG--- 156
** *****
```

CLUSTAL O(1.2.4) multiple sequence alignment

```

A.odend_synthetic      CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGGAAAGTTACGATAGATTGACTCT      60
A.odendhali_28S        CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGGAAAGTTACGATAGATTGACTCT      60
A.viteae_28S           CCAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGAAGAGTTACGATAGATTGACTTT      60
A.vit_synthetic        -----CATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAGAAGAGTTACGATAGATTGACTTT      54
D.rep_synthetic        ----TCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTATGGTAGATTATACTTT      56
D.repens_28S           -CAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTATGGTAGATTATACTTT      59
G17_amplicon           -CAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTATGGTAGATTATACTTT      59
D.immitis_28S          -CAGTCCATAGAAGGTGCTAGACCTGTACGGGTGAAAAAAGTTACGATATGTTATACTTT      59
D.imm_synthetic        -----GGTGAAAAAAGTTACGATATGTTATACTTT      30
                        ***** * ***** * ** ** ***** *
    
```

```

A.odend_synthetic      GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      120
A.odendhali_28S        GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      120
A.viteae_28S           GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      120
A.vit_synthetic        GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      114
D.rep_synthetic        GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      116
D.repens_28S           GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      119
G17_amplicon           GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      119
D.immitis_28S          GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      119
D.imm_synthetic        GGAGTCGGGTTGTTTGAGATTGCAGCCCAAAGAGGGTGGTAAACCTCATCTAAGGCTAAA      90
                        *****
    
```

```

A.odend_synthetic      TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG---- 157
A.odendhali_28S        TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG---- 157
A.viteae_28S           TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG---- 157
A.vit_synthetic        TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG---- 151
D.rep_synthetic        TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG---- 153
D.repens_28S           TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG---- 156
G17_amplicon           TACGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG---- 156
D.immitis_28S          TATGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAG---- 156
D.imm_synthetic        TATGACCACGAGACCGATAGCAAACAAGTACCGTGAGAAT 130
                        ** *****
    
```